

CHALLENGES OF HEALTH AWARENESS AND HIV/AIDS AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN RIVERINE AREAS OF THE URUAN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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ABSTRACT

HIV is a living virus that has invaded the human race for decades without the human race being able to find a permanent or lasting cure for the virus. In African societies, many factors have contributed to the striving pace of the virus, which is why this descriptive research sought to examine the challenges of health awareness and HIV/AIDS among adolescents in the riverine areas of Uruan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The Health Belief Model was adopted as a theoretical framework. The researchers used a simple random sampling technique to get the study participants. A questionnaire was used as a data collection instrument for the study. The gathered data were analysed descriptively. A comparative analysis was drawn using the Likert scale and percentage as major techniques in the data analysis. The findings from the study reveal that creating more awareness towards the existence and the effect of the disease will help reduce the spread of the scourge. It also reveals that the disease has a great effect on the cognitive development of the victims. Among the recommendations, the researchers opined that there should be a refocus of attention to rural communities and riverine areas where inhabitants, especially adolescents and young people may be ignorant of the situation and easily fall prey to victims in their adventure bid.

KEYWORDS: HIV/AIDS, Health awareness, Adolescents and Riverine areas.

INTRODUCTION

The acronym HIV/AIDS which means Human Immune Deficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome respectively have been in existence in Nigeria for over four decades ever since its discovery in 1980 killing thousands of people and rendering a lot orphans and childless. According to the National Aids and STD Control Programme (2001), HIV is a retrovirus disease that affects certain body cells and disease in the body's Immune System (Cells and Macrophages), which plays very important roles in fighting disease. The

virus, when inside the cells, multiplies itself and from there goes to infect other cells. This causes the infected cells to function improperly and die prematurely by weakening the immune and defence of human body the system and allowing for the development of various opportunistic infections such as diarrhoea, tuberculosis, skin rashes etc in the body of the victim.

Scientifically, HIV is a living organism (Virus) that can only thrive in the body fluid (blood). The virus can be transmitted when the fluid (blood) from an infected person enters the body of another; with the resultant and gradual destruction of the body's immune system rendering it to secondary (or opportunistic) infection. That is to say, HIV has to enter the body for infection to occur. On the other hand, AIDS can be described as the condition where the defence/immune system of an HIV-infected person(s) is destroyed resulting in full-blown symptoms. AIDS is the symptomatic stage of HIV disease and always terminates in death, since there is no scientifically developed cure and where the infection has not been treated.

HIV/AIDS is indeed a major public health concern to Nigeria which federal governments and other donor agencies should come together and address or drastically reduce the spread. It is of great danger and threat to the nation at large leading to a high rate of infant mortality (Ben and Daniel 2023), affecting also the youth population and thus should not be treated with levity. The major symptoms include among others marked weight loss, chronic fever that might last for a few months, and chronic diarrhoea (frequent stooling) lasting three months or more. Other features include persistent cough, skin rashes, swelling of the lymph nodes around the neck and ear region, tiredness, forgetfulness as well as mouth thrush.

Unlike many diseases, AIDS affects individuals in the most productive years, with the majority of those infected in people between the ages of 20 and 40 (Nnorom Ben 2001 and Daniel 2023; Daniel 2015) The above view was collaborated by Nigerian Aids Monitor (2010) which asserts that youths are particularly vulnerable to HIV/AIDS because of the high-risk behaviours they engage in. Such behaviours indeed is a reflection of the moral or decadence inherent in Nigerian society (Nana and Udom, 2024), and the prohibition concerning indecent sex attracts disapproval and punishment, serving as a deterrent to would-be offenders and thus engendering positive values through abstention.

Most importantly vulnerability is related to several factors including the extent to which individuals are born, grow and become sexually active, ignorance of the existence and mode of spread of HIV/AIDS, including preventive measures, belief systems and attitudes of individuals, especially youths to the existence of the disease.

Against the backdrop of the rapid report of the spread and challenges of the disease among adolescents. However, it is believed that their attitudes and negative thoughts might have contributed effectively, to worsening the already acute situation. This however, informed the institution of this study to assess the challenges of HIV/AIDS awareness and the spread of community health thus enhancing the need for more community awareness among adolescents in Riverine areas of Uruan LGA and the need to create more awareness targeted towards reducing the incident.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Generally, the study will assess adolescents' level of awareness of HIV/AIDS in Riverine areas of Uruan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study will;

- (i) examine awareness as a factor in the spread of HIV/AIDS
- (ii) investigate if HIV/AIDS disease has any impact on the cognitive development of Adolescent

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reproductive health and sex-related rules are introduced early in the lives of people in all communities. However, these patterns are affected by a series of factors of socialization ranging from socio-cultural and economic through peer pressures, and mass media and mostly based on the cultural belief that such issues are too delicate for them considering their tenderness and immaturity despite their expressed desire to know and be properly informed (Nnorom, 2001).

Nnorom, (2001) further noted that societies all over the world have come to see the importance of educating this young but very vulnerable group. Adolescents are daring, more than any other group, when it comes to experimentation and exploring new and unknown grounds. In so doing they may indulge in behaviour that may expose them to greater risks of contracting the virus that causes AIDS such as unprotected sexual activity and drug use, their tender nature also predisposes them to greater exploitation by the older ones. All these combine to make them more vulnerable.

It was based on the above that the United Nations set aside every 1st December as World HIV/AIDS day to create awareness of the existence, dangers and spread of the epidemic, as well as to avert its dangers on time. On the strength of the above Daniel and Ben (2024) recommended a timely awareness creation and sensitization of the victims, partners and the general public on the urgent need to reduce the scourge and as well put moralities/utilize the existing one for the treatment of HIV/AIDS.

HIV/AIDS Impact on Adolescent

The HIV/AIDS pandemic has of devastating effect on both children and adolescents as well as the society at large. Studies by Daniel (2010) show that 12 million children are orphaned by AIDS, nearly 600,000 infants are infected every year through mother to child and millions of young people live with the stigma of HIV but without access to adequate counseling or support. With HIV/AIDS and related diseases, human potential is reduced, human resources are wasted, and a complex mix of social and political problems are created making life and progress more difficult.

Orphans have alarmingly higher rates of malnutrition, stunting and illiteracy. Often their community shuns them, presuming that they too harbour the fatal virus. This makes the children suffer from severe psychological breakdowns due to the stigmatization of the people infected by the disease or the children of those affected. Relatives who often take them in, often seize their paltry inheritance and local laws offer little recourse to these vulnerable children. Further, children whose parents have died of the disease often must shoulder heavier workloads and are treated more harshly than the foster family's children (Chukuezi, 2002). According to Chukuezi, they are less likely to go to school and more likely to be depressed. Some of these orphans are simply abandoned to fend for themselves. Smith (2008), notes further that victim children live on the streets, and are made victims of social setbacks.

In Africa, the young girls are especially vulnerable. For instance, a study in Kenya shows that 25% of girls between the ages of 15 and 19 who were found to be HIV positive compared to 4% of the boys in the same age group were less able to relate with the larger

society after they had commenced treatment (Stephen, 2010). Also in Zambia survey showed that the rate among all teenage girls (12%) is nearly three times that of teenage boys (Nigeria Aids Monitor, 2017). Higher prevalence rates among girls reflect their biological vulnerability to infection, their social and physical vulnerability in sexual relations and the impact of gender discrimination in society.

According to Daniel (2011), in many of these diseases, the economic impact remains difficult to measure, but no doubt increased healthcare expenditures and loss of family income are straining resources, burdening women in particular and putting surviving children at greater risk of malnutrition, illiteracy, disease and death. Particularly, antiretroviral drugs which are used for the treatment of HIV/AIDS though given free are hard to come by and not within the reach of every patient. AIDS according to Stephen (2010) is decimating the ranks of the skilled and the educated during their prime years, with potentially tragic implications for future development.

HIV/AIDS Crisis in Nigeria

Since the early 80s when the first case of AIDS was diagnosed in the country, the disease has spread at an alarming rate. A report from the Federal Ministry of Health shows that as of 2023, 1910405 AIDS cases were passively reported in the country. This figure indicates that there is an alarming increase in the spread of HIV/AIDS in Nigeria. The reasons for the increase in number are not far-fetched. It shows that the infection is ravaging the country and there is also an increase in awareness as more people are going for screening.

The data further indicates that the number of new cases of HIV infections is progressively increasing in the country. Experts blame this scenario on inadequate facilities and capabilities for clinical and biomedical research on HIV/AIDS in various communities as well as on the attitude of people toward the existence of HIV/AIDS.

Inadequate facilities The Federal Ministry of Health has also been identified as preventing the generation of inadequate information on the clear figure of the disease in the country. Further, it has not been possible to verify the various claims for HIV treatment in the country as well as to initiate research for the development of curative and preventive vaccines in the country. The effects therefore according to Daniel (2011) is that we have to rely on data from the UN, World Bank and the developed countries for our control programmes.

Reasons for the spread of the HIV/AIDS virus

Writing on the Healthcare Model Peters and Daniel (2024) noted that the predisposing factors which in this case include ignorance, unprotected sex, and poverty thus making the party vulnerable: - enabling factors having to do with the belief system and availability of sex workers; the needs factors – sex being one of the psychological needs of man, and poor healthcare services are the crucial reasons HIV/AIDS epidemic has run out of control. Surveys indicate that many Africans are becoming aware that there is a sexually transmitted disease called AIDS, which is incurable, but they do not think the risk applies to them. Their vague knowledge does not translate into changes in their sexual behaviour. Thus, it is easy to see why so many do not yet sense the danger when few talk openly about the disease. Again to acknowledge being inflicted by AIDS is to be branded an outcast. Those who are aware that they have contracted the virus go into hiding due to the heavy veil of shame that hangs over those with this disease (Chukuezi, 2002). Chukuezi (2002), notes further that sometimes people deny the fact that they have the disease because HIV is linked with sex. To the author,

this is so because, the Africans, feel they must keep private anything that has to do with sex. Some people become depressed and decide to make irrational decisions.

Daniel (2011), notes that another reason for the high rate of spread of HIV/AIDS in our society is the fact that they are a roster of perils – famine, war, violence, desperation, ethnic hatred, unemployment and poverty – that the delayed risk of AIDS ran low. Poverty, particularly the lack of good health services, and poor educational services plays a great part in the spread of the virus. The burden is great on the already inadequate healthcare systems.

In Nigeria as well as in other developing countries, the disease is increasing the cost of healthcare delivery. This increasing cost reduces the availability of healthcare services to the poor who feel the greatest impact. In many communities, healthy children whose parents have died of AIDS are at greater risk of dying from preventable diseases because their illness tends to be attributed to AIDS and this may be so untreated. Sometimes orphans and HIV positive children are less likely than other children to be immunized and to have their healthcare needs adequately met.

As against women in developing societies, HIV-positive women in industrialised countries who become pregnant receive the antiretroviral drug, zidovudine (ZDV, better known as AZT) from at least the 14th weeks of pregnancy and the drug is administered to infants for 6 weeks after birth (Medical Records, 2000) an expensive regimen. Access to caesarean section delivery and safe artificial feeding also reduces the risk of mother-to-child transmission. These facilities are still novel in developing countries like Nigeria, thus making the treatment of HIV/AIDS challenging in our society.

Problems in combating HIV/AIDS scourge

In his message to the conference on HIV/AIDS (Abuja, 2001) the United Nations Secretary-General, Kofi Annan, pointed out that “Official recognition of the problem is the first step towards dealing with it and the 'battle against AIDS is like a 3rd World War if we consider the number of people who had been killed already'.

However, as in most of the continent, the major impediment to contending the spread of the virus is a lack of awareness and the belief system in the most vulnerable segments of the population. For example, in a study by Daniel (2011), the findings revealed that people between the ages of 15 and 19 were found to not know how to protect themselves from being infected by the virus. This is mostly for the rural population.

In a similar study by Ben, Daniel and Peters (2023), it was revealed that a greater percentage of victims of infections were not aware of the protective measures against them. Another problem according to Daniel (2011), was that of the attitude of people towards the use of condoms and of their belief on the existence of HIV/AIDS. In the study, it was revealed that 69 per cent of the respondents did not use condoms in sex believing that HIV/AIDS was manipulation from the witchcraft world. To some, they cannot make use of a condom because, without it, there is no sexual satisfaction. To this set of respondents, Daniel submits that they believe death can come from any direction since as mortals all men must die. In sum, Daniel notes that the problem of combating HIV/AIDS include a lack of awareness and poor attitudes of the people, poor government programmes, illiteracy as well as the belief system of the people, and negative relationship between the victim and other members of the society, are of serious challenge.

Prevention of HIV/AIDS virus

Chukuezi (2001), Daniel (2011) and Stephen (2010) conveyed three strong reassuring signals to developing countries. First, the authors noted that these societies have moved from the denial of the reality of the HIV scourge to a sober and critical acceptance of its existence as a major health problem of the continent. For too long African governments for example have done little to control HIV/AIDS (NACA, 2010). Africa allegedly accounts for about two-thirds of the global population of persons living with HIV/AIDS.

Though African leaders indeed agreed to place the fight against HIV/AIDS at the forefront and as the highest priority, issues of their respective national development plans hinder the struggle against the scourge. They resolved to allocate at least 15 per cent of their country's budget to the fight against HIV/AIDS and other related diseases. Other consensus reached includes the consolidation of the foundations of the prevention and control of the scourge through a comprehensive multi-sectional strategy, which, will involve all appropriate development sectors of governments. African governments have however taken responsibility and as well provided leadership for the activities of the National AIDS Commission Council, making the anti-retroviral drugs and as well as creating more awareness on AIDS.

However, the problem observed by Daniel (2011) remains the fact of what the individual can do to help prevent the disease from further spread. In both industrialized and developing countries interventions aimed at the young and awareness creation have proven to be the most effective and cost-efficient method for addressing the crisis in the long term. Education is paramount because it can empower people with the knowledge they need to protect themselves from infection. Also only education can combat the discrimination that helps perpetuate the pandemic. Education is very necessary to help children and young people acquire the knowledge and develop skills they need to build a better future and this awareness should be rooted in the Primary School.

In the most comprehensive review of sexual health education undertaken by UNAIDS findings show that good education does help delay first intercourse and protect sexually active behaviour among young people in rural areas, other sexually transmitted disease also reduces the rate of unwanted pregnancy which is prevalent among the adult population. The benefits of education have been proven most explicitly in underdeveloped as well as other third world countries and this creates awareness among people and thus enhances the protective measures among young people thus reducing the scourge.

A CASE FOR RIVER BASED STUDIES; URUAN LGA OF AKWAIBOM STATE

Riverine inhabitants are known to have an isolated mentality probably associating HIV/AIDS as an urban phenomenon and believing that the disease discriminates in favour of riverine dwellers. Despite the fact the riverine areas are known for the abuse of drugs (Peters and Bassey, 2020), there is a need to inform them that the problems and challenges posed by the disease can affect any community anywhere notwithstanding its location. To do this effectively, riverine inhabitants must be informed of this message in their environment and be made to realize that someone in the small community somewhere may be infected with HIV/AIDS and either do not know it or is unable to say so for fear of being stigmatized or the family facing sanction from the society.

For this to be achieved, correct and adequate information must be made available to the riverine populace especially adolescents and young people who may likely fall prey to

sexual advances. That is why there is a need to ascertain the extent of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS among the riverine populace especially the young people who are very vulnerable and venture into risky behaviour. Such studies will form the basis from which appropriate health intervention programmes will be formulated.

Riverine inhabitants also lack basic health facilities which is a key determinant to the accessibility of health care services (Ononokpono, Peters and Usoro, 2019), and even where they are in existence, they are not equipped to face the challenges of modern times such as providing testing centres for HIV/AIDS which create rooms for unorthodox abuse of orthodox medicine through the vendors (Wilson, Usoro and Peters, 2020). Although the urban centres are an as well challenge not better placed in this case, centres exist where doctors can refer their suspected patients for testing if need be. For this singular reason, most inhabitants in the rural community are left in the dark as regards their health status and a lot are still hoping for medically prescribed drugs (Peters, Bassey and Nya, 2020). Since HIV/AIDS takes time to manifest physically, many of the rural dwellers believe they are healthy and go about infecting unsuspecting sexual partners.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Health Belief Model (HBM). This is one of the most known models of treatment-seeking behaviour. According to Secran and Abraham (1995), the Health Belief Model is guided by the following assumptions:

- (1) Beliefs about the impact of the illness and its consequences (threat perception). This threat perception depends on:
 - * Perceived susceptibility, or the belief about how vulnerable a person considers him or herself about a certain illness or health problem.
 - * Perceived severity of illness or health problems and its consequences
- (2) Health motivation, or readiness to be concerned about health matters.
- (3) Beliefs about the consequences of health practices and about the possibilities and efforts to put them into practice. This behavioural evaluation depends on the following factors;
 - * Perceived benefits of preventive or therapeutic health practices.
 - * Perceived barriers, both material and psychological (or example willpower), with regards to a certain health practice.
- (4) Owing to action, which includes different internal and external factors which influence action. For example the nature and intensity (organic and symbolic) of illness symptoms, mass media campaigns, and advice from relevant others (family, friends health staff).
- (5) Beliefs and health motivation are conditioned by socio-demographic variables (class, age, gender, religion) and by psychological characteristics of the interviewed person (personality, peer group, pressure group etc). The socio-demographic variables target groups which are established to which interventions can be directed. These interventions are mainly health promotions and centre on beliefs about disease threats and behavioural evaluation. These are the factors which are considered to be transformable through health education to HIV/AIDS patients, in contrast to structural or cultural factors like poverty, religious norms, etc.

There is evidence that perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits and barriers of the Health Belief Model are relevant factors in treatment-seeking behaviours (Sheeran and

Abraham, 1995). The Health Belief Model (HBM) neglects further determinants which are present in other models like previous experiences, advantages of maladaptive behaviour, behavioural intention and perceived control. Through, the Health Belief Model, interesting and highly relevant findings for health promotion can be determined. For example, for a disease like HIV/AIDS which the riverine associate with urban centres, persons who do not live in these areas will hardly consider themselves vulnerable to the disease. This had particular implications for health messages about HIV/AIDS, which in later campaigns needed to be explicitly targeted at riverine areas like in Uruan in order to create risk awareness among the population.

RESULT

Certain fundamental issues primarily aimed at testing the awareness level of young people and the rate of spread of HIV/AIDS as well as the impact of the disease on their cognitive development in Uruan were raised. The responses from the respondents are tabulated and their attitudes are portrayed in a Likert scale format as follows:

- Strongly Agree (SA)
- Agree (A)
- Disagree (D)
- Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 1: Do you consider awareness as a factor in the spread of HIV/AIDS

	Name of villages	No. or respondents	SA	A	D	SD
A	Ishiet	28	18	7	3	-
B	Ifiayong	28	15	11	2	-
C	Eman Ukpa	30	13	12	4	1
D	Eman Usuk	30	20	9	-	1
E	Adadia	30	17	10	3	-
F	Esuk Odu	29	14	14	1	-
G	Ekpen Ibia	30	14	11	3	1
H	Ndom Ebom	30	10	16	2	2
I	Ituk Mbang	30	10	11	9	-
	Total	265	131	101	27	5

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Weighted mean

$$\begin{aligned}
 3 \quad SA &= 13 \times 4 = 524 \\
 3 \quad A &= 101 \times 3 = 303 \\
 2 \quad D &= 27 \times 2 = 54 \\
 1 \quad SD &= 5 \times 1 = 5
 \end{aligned}$$

Cross weighted mean = 886

Percentage of responses

$$SA = \frac{524}{886} \times \frac{100}{1} = 59\%$$

$$A = \frac{303}{886} \times \frac{100}{1} = 34\%$$

$$D = \frac{54}{886} \times \frac{100}{1} = 6\%$$

$$SD = \frac{5}{886} \times \frac{100}{1} = 0.6\%$$

∴ Positive responses = 59% + 34% = 93%
Negative responses = 6% + 0.6% = 6.6%

Table 2: Do you consider HIV/AIDS disease to have any impact on the cognitive development of Adolescent

	Name of villages	No. or respondents	SA	A	D	SD
A	Ishiet	28	23	2	2	-
B	Ifiayong	28	19	7	1	1
C	Eman Ukpa	30	26	4	-	-
D	Eman Usuk	30	18	10	-	-
E	Adadia	30	15	15	-	-
F	Esuk Odu	29	15	12	-	1
G	Ekpen Ibia	30	20	10	-	-
H	Ndom Ebom	30	11	17	1	-
I	Ituk Mbang	30	17	12	-	-
	Total	265	164	89	4	2

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Weighted mean

$$4 \quad SA = 164 \times 4 = 656$$

$$A = 89 \times 3 = 267$$

$$D = 4 \times 2 = 8$$

$$SD = 2 \times 1 = 2$$

Cross weighted mean = 933

Percentage of responses

$$SA = \frac{656}{933} \times \frac{100}{1} = 70\%$$

$$A = \frac{267}{933} \times \frac{100}{1} = 29\%$$

$$D = \frac{8}{933} \times \frac{100}{1} = 0.9\%$$

$$SD = \frac{2}{933} \times \frac{100}{1} = 0.2\%$$

$$\therefore \begin{aligned} \text{Positive responses} &= 70\% + 29\% = 99\% \\ \text{Negative responses} &= 0.9\% + 0.2\% = 1.1\% \end{aligned}$$

FINDINGS

The analysis of Tables 1 and 2 shows that the awareness level of people and their knowledge as well as attitudes toward HIV/AIDS and prevention methods affect the spread of the disease in the riverine area of Uruan. In Table 1, findings show that of the 265 respondents 131 (59%) agreed strongly that there is a need to create more awareness among the people on the existence of the disease, its effect and the prevention method among the people. In all, the positive responses as regards the knowledge and awareness level was 935 while 6% disagreed on this.

In Table 2, the findings reveal that 164 of the persons examined strongly agree that HIV/AIDS disease has a great impact on the personality of children. 89 equally agreed on this while 4 and 2 disagree and strongly disagree respectively. In sum, the positive responses stood at 99% as against 1% for negative responses on whether HIV/AIDS has any impact on the cognitive development of victims.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The focus of this study centred on community health and the challenges of HIV/AIDS. The need for more community awareness among young people in the Riverine Area of Uruan Local Government Area. The study attempted to identify the level of people's awareness, knowledge and perception of HIV/AIDS as well as the impact of the disease on the cognitive development of young people. To assess the awareness level of the existence and prevention of the disease (HIV/AIDS), a sample size of 270 respondents selected from the study area was adopted. Data for the research were collected using a questionnaire and structured interview schedule. A comparative analysis was drawn using the Likert scale and percentage as major techniques in the data analysis.

Findings from the study reveal that creating more awareness towards the existence and the effect of the disease will help reduce the spread of the scourge. It also reveals that the disease has a great effect on the cognitive development of the victims.

CONCLUSION

The study further assesses the knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS as well as its challenges in the riverine area of Uruan Local Government Area. The study reveals that despite the concentration of different studies, governments and Non-Governmental Organisation's efforts in reducing the scourge and rate of the disease in the study area remain alarming. The study reveals that the sexual behaviour of those equipped with the right knowledge remains highly unchanged indicating a possibility of higher HIV transmission and AIDS in society, thus the need for more awareness.

The study shows that the rural inhabitants lack appropriate information because of a lack of studies and information dissemination and face the danger of contracting the disease of the exploratory and risky behaviours adolescents and young people exhibit in this bid to taste new worlds.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Taking into consideration the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. A refocus of attention to rural communities and riverine areas where inhabitants, especially adolescents and young people may be ignorant of the situation and easily fall prey to victims in their adventure bid.
2. More awareness should be created on the dangers of unprotected sex and the use of condoms in every pre-marital sex.
3. NGOs, government institutions and individuals should be involved in rehabilitating AIDS victims.
4. The government should establish test centres in every community, especially in the riverine areas to identify people's status and further treatment of victims.
5. Laws protecting AIDS patients from being victimized by family, friends, and organizations by pose into law to help reduce socio-psychological and economic pressure on them.
6. Governments should propose and establish mobile clinics where health centres are not possible.

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